

INDICATORS REVEALING THE SPECIAL WORK CAPACITY OF QUALIFIED ROWERS SPECIALIZED IN SPRINTING

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A special 40-second test (on a rowing ergometer) was conducted, revealing the special work capacity and functional state of the subjects (Table 12). When comparing the initial results of the test control, no significant differences were observed between the control and experimental groups [$P>0.05$]. At the end of the study, the rowing power of the experimental group subjects in the 40-second rowing test was 388.1W, the number of strokes during the test was 104.3, the rowing speed was 5.8 m/s, and the distance covered in 40 seconds was 218.4 m. In the control group, these indicators were 350.5W, 95.7, 4.9 m/s, and 207.2 m, respectively.

Table 1

Indicators of the experimental and control group subjects according to the 40-second rowing test at the beginning and end of the experiment

No	Indicators	EG		t	p	CG		t	p
		beginnin g	end			beginnin g	end		
		$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$	$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$			$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$	$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$		
1	Rowing power, W	345.7±7.6	388.1±9.2	2.01	<0.05	347.0±8.3	350.5±5.9	1.68	>0.05
2	Number of strokes	92.5±3.6	104.3±4.7	2.10	<0.05	93.8±2.9	95.7±4.1	1.45	>0.05
3	Rowing speed, m/s	4.6±0.3	5.8±0.6	2.08	<0.05	4.7±0.8	4.9±0.5	1.77	>0.05
4	Distance in 40s, m	205.7±4.5	218.4±3.9	2.16	<0.05	204.1±2.8	207.2±3.7	1.65	>0.05
5	La 3-min recovery, mMol/l	12.5±1.6	9.7±0.8	2.12	<0.05	11.9±1.3	10.5±1.0	1.71	>0.05
6	La 8-min recovery, mMol/l	10.2±1.1	6.5±0.4	2.07	<0.05	10.7±1.4	9.8±0.6	1.68	>0.05
7	HR 1-min recovery, bpm	145.7±8.6	137.4±7.2	2.25	<0.05	143.3±9.1	141.0±6.8	1.91	>0.05
8	Heart rate 2 min recovery bpm	131.8±7.9	122.7±4.7	2.18	<0.05	130.6±8.9	128.8±7.9	1.54	>0.05
9	Heart rate 3 min recovery bpm	119.2±5.4	109.9±3.7	2.24	<0.05	117.4±6.1	114.5±4.7	1.72	>0.05

Note:

The analysis of indicators revealed that no statistically significant differences were observed between the indicators of the control group subjects [$p > 0.05$].

We can observe differences with positive dynamics between the results obtained at the beginning and end of the study in determining the special work capacity and functional state of the experimental group subjects [$p < 0.05$].

During the study period, a tendency towards a significant increase in the metabolic capabilities of athletes was identified. In relation to the oxidation mechanism of energy supply, this was manifested in an increase in the power and efficiency of the aerobic energy supply mechanism during work. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Results of the experimental and control group subjects obtained at the beginning of the study on the 40-second rowing test

Figure 2. Results of the experimental and control group subjects obtained at the end of the study on the 40-second rowing test

Regarding the lactate mechanism of energy supply, an increase in glycolysis power was observed. At the end of the study, according to the 40-second rowing test, the lactate concentration in the blood of the subjects in the experimental group was 9.7 mMol/l at the 3rd minute of recovery and 6.5 mMol/l at the 8th

minute of recovery. Analysis of the obtained results reveals statistically significant differences with positive dynamics [$p \leq 0.05$]. In the control group, the lactate concentration in the blood was 10.5 mMol/l at the 3rd minute of recovery and 9.8 mMol/l at the 8th minute of recovery. Consequently, the indicators of the subjects in the experimental group were superior to those of the subjects in the control group [$p < 0.05$]. This indicates a significant increase in the capacity of the lactate mechanism of energy supply in rowers of the experimental group.

To assess the cardiovascular system's response to exertion and work capacity at the beginning and end of the study, we decided to measure heart rate during the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd minutes of recovery following a 40-second rowing test. No statistically significant differences were observed between the initial results in each group [$p > 0.05$]. At the conclusion of the study, the experimental group's heart rates were 137.4, 122.7, and 109.9 beats per minute during the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd minutes of recovery, respectively. For the control group, these values were 141.0, 128.8, and 114.5 beats per minute. This reveals statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups' indicators. The experimental group's subjects demonstrated superior results compared to the control group [$p < 0.05$]. We can observe that these recorded indicators fully align with the high level of special work capacity achieved.

Conclusion: Special work abilities are a crucial factor in the effective performance of qualified rowers specializing in sprint. During the study, athletes' indicators such as speed, strength, reaction time, starting technique, and running mechanics were evaluated as factors directly influencing their overall results. It was also determined that individual physiological and psychological characteristics, level of preparedness, and the effectiveness of training processes play a key role in achieving high results. The research findings serve as an important scientific and practical basis for athlete selection, improving their training system, and achieving high results in competitions.

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